

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and the Electron Mass

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the 8T framework and in particular the electron, i.e. the invariant three alongside the symmetry break associated with mass, i.e. the 8 – (1) variations, it is possible to explain why the electron has mass. The reason is it is associated with a number belonging to the symmetry break of mass creation. Analysis will be done using the primordial coupling constants series, in the first representation, net curvature on the varying Lorentz manifold.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). by (1.2) those equations are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \quad (1.43)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Electron has absorbed a discrete amount of net curvature, its energy increased. Since we are familiar with the equivalence relation between mass and energy, as presented by Albert Einstein, energy increase is synonymous with mass increase. The magnitude will stay as it is, invariantly of the actual particle. What will vary as a result of the particle varied is energy of the photon emitted.

Up to this point, reader is probably familiar with everything. In addition, from this point on, we have a completely new paper. Since mass is curvature converging inward, given by the Quark masses series, and this mass Series is associated with a symmetry break of the kind $8 - (1)$ variations, we can associate the electron to this group, by two reasons. First, it is itself the additional element breaking the symmetry of the series, appearing from the second term of the coupling constants series. The second since it is not a boson, it can not be associated with the symmetry break associated with the boson ripple propagation, or the inverse symmetry break of the $8 + (1)$ variations, denoted by equation (1.44). The bosons are spike curvature vortexes on the matric tensor of discrete amount, which belong to the prime numbers with long and stable lifetime.

$$(e) \notin 8 + (1) \tag{1.47}$$

The reason the electron does not belong to this group despite it has an element which is exactly similar to the electron value is due to its spin, which is one half not spin one, given by the additional term. So according to the 8T the electron must be associated with the inverse symmetry break which resulting in acquiring mass.

$$\left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] \rightarrow [2N_2 + (e)]$$

One final point before we finish, is that the result of two broken symmetries does not mean an additional broken symmetry. In the case of mass acquiring and boson propagation, those symmetry breaks vanish into a perfect symmetry which no net curvature is appearing, neither inward nor outward.

$$8 - (1) + 8 + (1) \rightarrow 0$$

That is the reason bosons with mass can propagate across like massless bosons, there is no net curvature converging, they will travel as a massless particle. That was the construction used to prove the Yang Mills problem, suggested by the 8T in 2021 by the author. We can make a prediction according to the 8T and state:

- (1) Bosons with mass propagate at the same speed as Massless Bosons
- (2) Massless particles are associated with no symmetry break toward $8 - (1)$ variations

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)